

Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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Abbreviations

CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
D	Deliverable
DOA	Description of Action
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
RI	Research Infrastructure
TM	Team Member(s)
TNA	Transnational Access
PPP	Preparatory Phase Project
USC	User Services Catalogue
USP	Unique Selling Point
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Introductory Notes

D4.3 is based on previous versions of the Communication & Dissemination Plan, D4.1 and D4.2. It gives an update of the communication strategies in alignment with the project results, as well as a first version of a dissemination strategy. It also looks ahead to the next phase.

The strategies in this Plan outline the key areas vision, mission, accountability, and game plan, considering the internal and external situation, stakeholders and resources. Besides, this document answers remaining questions from the previous deliverables, providing strategic measures where necessary, and reports on the past period: what is the progress made in achieving the goals and reaching target audiences with core messages. It also provides an outlook: How to evaluate the progress made considering the predefined KPIs and what recommendations to make for the future?

The above is based on the objectives in the GA, which are for WP4:

- updating and implementing the Communication & Dissemination Plan during the Preparatory Phase (delivered in resp. M5 and M30 via D4.1 and D4.2 and in M44 with D4.3)
- to develop a communication study dedicated to the specificity and typology of services and datasets for religious studies (delivered in M31 via D4.4).¹

1.2 Starting Points

For the definition of the strategies, as well as for the operational work done, following starting points from previous deliverables remain in force:

- An agile approach, resulting in an agile communication strategy (the three communication strategy frames).
- In the cycle of communication, both WU CDE and the consortium partners are multipliers, namely of each other's news, and initiators in the sense of supplying news and other announcements.
- Geographical preconditions: each partner is responsible for communication/dissemination in one or more European countries according to the previously defined geographical distribution.²

¹ Grant Agreement 101079792, part A., p. 9.

² RESILIENCE PPP Deliverable D4.1, 14-15.

- The use of Simon Sinek’s Golden Circle model,³ supporting presenters in tailoring messages to different target groups, thus ensuring a more effective connection to these groups. The values formulated in the vision/mission document can help in this respect.⁴
- The corporate design, which visualizes the dynamics of building the RI through various forms and shapes, developed in RESILIENCE’s Design Phase.⁵

³ See RESILIENCE PPP Deliverable D4.2, par. 2.7.

⁴ The vision/mission statement is online accessible via <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/we-are-resilience/vision-and-mission/>.

⁵ Deliverable D5.3, RESILIENCE Design Phase, Grant Agreement 871227.

2 Key Principles for Communication and Dissemination

2.1 Goals⁶

General Strategic Goals for RESILIENCE's Communication and Dissemination

- 1 Raising awareness about RESILIENCE.
- 2 Influencing target audiences in their perception of RESILIENCE (their perception develops into a growing awareness of the need of an RI for the study of religion, as well as knowing how to make use of it).

Specific Strategic Goals for External Communication

- 1 Spreading information about the RI.
- 2 Attracting target audiences, so that they can play an active part in the Preparatory Phase and thereafter.

2.2 Target Audiences

Below are the relevant target groups for our communication and dissemination activities. All target groups and respective subgroups can be approached with messages about developments within the project (communication) and with messages about the use of the services developed by the RI (dissemination), except for the media: they are primarily a target group when it comes to communication. More about the distinction between communication and dissemination is explained in par. 3.1.

ACADEMIC (Communication and Dissemination)

- Professors.
- Experts.
- Scholars and students.
- Research and/or educational institutions.
- Members of RIs and other research networks in Europe.⁷

⁶ NB. Specific Strategic Goals for Internal Communication (Supporting partners find their role in the communication and dissemination activities; Achieving the highest level of participation by all partners in communication and dissemination activities) have not been carried over from D4.2, as they have been achieved in view of the progress made in the project and the ongoing and improving cooperation.

⁷ RESILIENCE is interested in entering a proactive relationship with other European projects and RIs related in the field, because it expects to benefit from them and it expects that there will be a mutual benefit (synergy). Other European projects and RIs are, for example, CLARIN and DARIAH. Because of the aim of a relationship, it is most effective to start with connections on a management level (directors connect with directors), the level where the decisions are made. Starting 2019, the following contacts have been made: CLARIN ERIC, CLARIN IT, CLARIAH, DARIAH ERIC, CESSDA ERIC, EHRI, IPERION, EOSC, OSCARS,

- Libraries.

NON-ACADEMIC (Communication and Dissemination)

- Professionals in religious communities or churches.
- NGOs.
- Civil Society.

NEW PARTNERS (Communication and Dissemination)

- GLAM-Institutions (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums).
- Potential business investors (to be defined in a later stage).
- New partners from not yet represented countries.⁸

DECISION MAKERS (Communication and Dissemination)

- Governmental institutions or organisations.
- Policy makers.

MEDIA (Communication)

- Television and radio.
- Newspapers.

2.3 Core Messages

To arrive at core messages and a clear set of sub-messages from the vision/mission document, grounded in the services RESILIENCE will offer to the future users of the RI, the Message House model was used. In keeping with WP3 Services' choice of three archetypes (Researchers, Librarians and Archivists), the Message House is filled out for these audiences.

NB. Here an explanation of the role of archetypes and other groups mentioned in D4.3 Documented Use Cases 2nd batch, as well as in D4.2, the previous version of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan seems to be adequate:

- Archetypes.
- User Groups.

SSHOC, E-RIHS, H2IOSC, Time Machine Organisation, EUROPEANA, and EATRIS ERIC, Euro-Biolmaging ERIC, eRImote, Skills4EOOSC, VEREAD, Science Europe, Eastern Christian Studies - Online Campus, University Research Priority Program (URPP) 'Digital Religions', University of Zürich.

⁸ The General Assembly of RESILIENCE appointed an Enlargement Committee, which is addressing this target group.

- Target audiences.
- Stakeholders.

The *archetypes* describe a pattern and show why people want to make use of a specific service, whereas the term *user groups* refers to a specific segment of users defined by who they are and how they use a service. *User groups* describe who uses the research infrastructure, while *target audiences* define who is strategically addressed through communication and outreach activities. *Stakeholders* represent those who have an interest in or influence on the infrastructure, and *archetypes* mediate between stakeholders and user groups by abstracting their needs to inform infrastructure design and targeted engagement.

For the time being, the archetypes selected by WP3 have been chosen for the formulation of core messages in the Message House, but it is recommended that the next version of the dissemination strategy be tailored more closely to the archetypes.

All other messages for different target audiences are defined in the communication matrix (table 1). The messages in the partner matrices (see Attachment 3 of D4.2) can be further tailored towards different target audiences and contexts using the Golden Circle Model.⁹ The core messages in the Message Houses are related to the 5 elements of our vision and mission statement, whereas the numbers in fig. 1 and fig. 2 refer to the components below:

RESILIENCE:

1. serves research on religion.
2. offers access to digital and physical sources.
3. brings in innovation.
4. strives for open and FAIR access.
5. improves knowledge on and understanding of religion.¹⁰

⁹ See RESILIENCE PPP Deliverable D4.2, par. 2.7.

¹⁰ The shortest message concerning the RI is summarized in the slogan "Serving Research, Building Knowledge".

Figure 1 Message House with Core Messages for Academics

Figure 2 Message House with Core Messages for Librarians and Archivists

2.4 Tools, Channels and Touchpoints

For internal and external communication, several tools, channels and touchpoints have been developed. They are constantly under review, to enable updates.¹¹ Tools and Channels for Internal Communication are: E-mail, email lists, email signature, project management tool (ClickUp), video conference, online project repository, guides, face to face meetings, communication toolkit, action plan.

The touchpoints¹² for External Communication are: Website, newsletter, social media channels, keywords, PPT-template, stationary, word templates, excel template, press release format, press contact list, business cards, posters and flyers, banner, noteblock, videos, hashtags, YouTube, face to face contacts, personal contacts, traditional media (newspapers, journals etc.) and panels at the annual conference of the European Academy of Religion.

2.5 Communication Matrix

For previous versions of D4.3, a communication matrix (then called generic partner matrix) was established. This matrix is meant to support WP4 and the partners in their communication and dissemination activities, because via the matrix they get a quick overview of target audiences, their needs, core messages, tools, channels and touchpoints to be used and specific goals to be achieved.

Each partner communicates in English as its main language and decides per communication or dissemination activity whether it is necessary to communicate in the native language of their target audience as well. For some partners in the Eastern European and Balkan areas, the native language of the target audiences sometimes differs from their own native language.

Each target audience is served via a specified number of tools, channels and touchpoints: In the generic partner matrix below, you can find the numbers of the tools, channels or touchpoints that are used per audience. The numbers relate to:

1. Website.
2. Newsletter.
3. Flyers/posters.
4. Press Releases.
5. Videos.
6. Social Media channels (partners choose their own preferred channels, such as Facebook, X (Twitter) or Instagram).

¹¹ See for further definition of the tools, channels and touchpoints RESILIENCE PPP Deliverable D4.1, p. 80-98.

¹² All moments and interfaces when a target audience "touches" RESILIENCE somehow.

7. Face to face collaboration (this applies only to the Preparatory Phase, and divides into different categories, as explained in par. 10.10).
8. Conferences/workshops and other events.
9. Self-owned Media channels.
10. Personnel contacts.
11. Panels at the annual conference of the European Academy of Religion.
12. Traditional media (newspapers, journals).

Each partner is responsible for how frequently they communicate, and chooses its own preferred tools, channels or touchpoints.

To serve the target audience best, their interests and needs, specific messages have been added to the communication matrix. These messages have been derived from the core messages and adapted with the interests and needs of the target audiences in mind, as currently understood:

Target Audience	Interest/Need	Specific Message	Tools, Channels and Touchpoints
<i>Category: Academic</i>			
Professors	They want facilitated access to scientific resources, they want to expand their community and their international network, and they want to offer expert assistance in solving ongoing political and religious issues.	RESILIENCE offers you a unique gateway to resources and services for the study of religion.	1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
Experts	They want facilitated access to scientific resources; they want to expand their community; to expand their international network and they want to offer expert assistance in solving ongoing political and religious issues.	RESILIENCE offers you a unique gateway to resources related to the study of religion.	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
Scholars and students	They want to develop their career, exchange new ideas, get publicity for their research output, enter the academic network and expand their academic contacts.	RESILIENCE creates new opportunities for knowledge exchange and networking.	1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11
Research and/or educational institutions	They want facilitated access to scientific resources, to expand their user community	RESILIENCE enhances research on religion and increases your visibility.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11

Target Audience	Interest/Need	Specific Message	Tools, Channels and Touchpoints
	and gain international contacts. They are able to share their own data and output.		
Members of other RI and research networks in Europe	They want to make use of the expertise of other institutions, and they want to cooperate to create synergy. They want to expand their network with new researchers or RIs.	RESILIENCE is open to cooperation and offers its expertise to you.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11
Libraries	They want to serve their users with the latest data and data tools. They want to make their holdings accessible and more visible to others and be up to date with new developmental instruments and/or products.	RESILIENCE helps you to optimize the service to your users and makes others aware of your resources.	1, 2, 6, 7
Category: Non-academic			
Professionals in religious communities or churches	Facing the challenges of a multi-religious society, they want easy access to reliable knowledge and to experts in the field.	RESILIENCE offers you a unique access to scientific-based knowledge and to experts in the field of the study of religion.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11
Relevant NGOs (e.g. humanitarian or religious organisations)	They need knowledge on topics related to religion (issues, practices, etc.).	RESILIENCE shares with you science-based information, facilitates contacts with experts in the field and helps you find relevant information.	4, 6, 10
Civil Society ¹³	Facing the challenges of a multi-religious society, they want to know how to deal with these challenges.	RESILIENCE shares with you science-based information and expertise on issues related to religion.	6, 12
Category: New Partners			
GLAM institutions	They want affordable use of the newest tools and techniques related to collections. They want to enlarge the audience for their collections. They want access to the latest research-based insights on religion	RESILIENCE helps you to strengthen your specific and essential role in research, offers you the latest research-based insights on	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 10

¹³ By civil society we mean that part of society is meant to be organized by and representing citizens in independent foundations, associations etc., promoting social cohesion and strengthening the influence of citizens.

Target Audience	Interest/Need	Specific Message	Tools, Channels and Touchpoints
		religion and increases your visibility.	
Potential business investors	They want to make money and a good impression and see an opportunity to do so via RESILIENCE.	RESILIENCE opens up new markets for you.	1, 2, 6, 10
New partners from not yet represented countries	They constantly look for ways to better reach their goals, such as facilitated access to scientific resources or expanding their community and/or their international network.	RESILIENCE is the right infrastructure to reach your goals.	1, 2, 3, 6, 10
Category: Decision Makers			
Governmental institutions or organisations	They need reliable information and easy access to expertise and experts	RESILIENCE shares with you science-based information, data and expertise to deal with religions.	1, 2, 4, 6, 10
Policy makers	They need information and expertise on topics related to the study of religion. They need convincing argumentation for the need of a separate RI for the study of religion.	RESILIENCE gives access to a wide range of information and expertise on religions. RESILIENCE facilitates multidisciplinary, data-intensive, and technology-supported research on the study of religion. It supports access to both physical and digital resources. ¹⁴	1, 2, 4, 6, 10
Category: Media			
Television and radio	They need easy access to information and to experts in the field of religion. They want to gather and communicate news on issues related to religion.	RESILIENCE offers you easy access to information and to a wide pool of experts, who can reflect and inform on current issues.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10
Newspapers	They need easy access to information and to experts in the field of religion. They want	RESILIENCE offers you easy access to information and to a wide pool of experts, who	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10

¹⁴ More can be read on the website: <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/we-are-resilience/need/>.

Target Audience	Interest/Need	Specific Message	Tools, Channels and Touchpoints
	to gather and communicate news on issues related to religion.	can reflect and inform on current issues.	
Online media	They need easy access to information and to experts in the field of religion. They want to gather and communicate news on issues related to religion.	RESILIENCE offers you easy access to information and to a wide pool of experts, who can reflect and inform on current issues.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10
Self-owned media channels	They need input related to the study of religion and ways to promote their institution.	RESILIENCE offers you ideas, topics, themes and a podium to present your institution and contents.	4, 10
Journalists	They need easy access to information and to experts in the field of religion. They want to gather and communicate news on issues related to religion.	RESILIENCE offers you easy access to information and to a wide pool of experts, who can reflect and inform on current issues.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10

Table 1 Communication Matrix

3 Communication and Dissemination Strategies

3.1 Introduction

The following section distinguishes between the communication and dissemination strategies. *Communication* is a strategically planned process of transmission of information, aimed at promoting the action and its results to multiple audiences, including media and the public. *Dissemination* is the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means - this includes scientific publications in any medium - with the aim of enabling others to use and take up results. Seen in this light, dissemination can be considered an extension of communication: target groups first learn about the RI and then understand how they can make concrete use of it.

RESILIENCE's dissemination strategy is still limited. In the past period of RESILIENCE's PPP, news about the TNA fellowships, ReIReSearch, and Zenodo has been disseminated, with the strongest emphasis on TNA. In the remaining months of the PPP and the next phase of the RI, there are no TNA fellowships planned. Meanwhile, the User Services Catalogue (USC), Deliverable D2.2, is available on Zenodo, an important step toward providing easy access to digital and physical data on religion, and relevant services via one access point. This version of the USC is primarily intended to provide an overview of what is available from partners, rather than to encourage the use and uptake of those services.¹⁵ For this reason, a dissemination "lite" strategy is included, focusing on USC. In a subsequent phase, this service strategy can then be converted into a separate and more robust dissemination strategy.

The Communication Strategy Frame has been taken as a guide for an agile development of the communication and dissemination strategy, defined in three frames:¹⁶

- A General Communication Strategy Frame.
- A Communication Strategy Frame for Eastern Europe and the Balkans.
- A Dissemination Strategy Frame for Services.

¹⁵ The USC as described in D2.2 will be presented on RESILIENCE's website early 2026 in the form of overviews of available services, aiming at visualizing service overviews and making target audiences aware of these services.

¹⁶ Based on B. van Ruler (2021), *Handboek communicatiestrategie. Agile methode voor strategie-ontwikkeling*, Amsterdam: Boom Uitgevers.

3.2 General Communication Strategy Frame

Below is the fourth version of the frame. Compared to the previous version¹⁷ and in view of developments within the consortium, the following changes have been made:

- Internal situation: Reference to the common compass was removed since it was no longer used or discussed internally in a direct way.
- Gameplan: for the next phase, consideration for a USP campaign has been added.
- Gameplan: the reference to the drafting of more events showing the innovative and digital character of the RI has been removed, because of prematurity in this phase. To be reconsidered after the publication of the services catalogue.
- Gameplan: for the next phase a strategy for reaching decision makers was added.
- Stakeholders: a reference was made to archetypes as defined by WU Users in general, avoiding the number of archetypes defined (since this is under construction).

¹⁷ Communication Strategy Frame 03.00, RESILIENCE PPP Deliverable D4.2, 25.

Internal Situation

- Increasing clarity about services that will be offered.
- The consortium works with a more defined vision/mission statement.
- RESILIENCE as the RI for the study of religion is moving towards full operation.

Vision

- RESILIENCE connects research centers, data holders and services distributed all over Europe and creates new instruments and services for its scientific community.
- RESILIENCE facilitates faster, better, and more efficient research, as well as access to online and physical sources. It offers a central place where to find evolving tools and big data.
- RESILIENCE enters the field of new developments of Open Science, offering FAIR access to data and storing data as well as to resources, tools, etc.
- Communication is integrated within the consortium and serves all WUs to reach their goals.

Accountability

- WU CDE uses the convincing narrative of the RI, (the updated vision/mission statement), sees to sufficient publicity. Other WUs will support this, and deliver content.
- TUA shares event feedback within the consortium.
- TUA organizes monitoring and reporting and supports partners in this respect.
- TUA supports the consortium in organizing workshops and events initiated by BOD.
- Partners redistribute news.
- Partners present RESILIENCE on events and in media, deliver content for website. TUA puts an emphasis on presentations.

Stakeholders

- Internal: WU CDE members.
- External: archetypes as defined by WU Users.
- Target Audiences: Academics, Non-academics (Religious Community, NGO's, civil society), Decision makers, New partners, Media.

External Situation

- Depending on their context, stakeholders can be convinced of the necessity of a RI for Religious Studies.
- Our audiences are interested in services that are up and running.

Ambition

- In 2026:**
- RESILIENCE is recognized in Europe and beyond as a unique and indispensable RI.
 - Target audiences are aware of the RI and of relevant developments within the WUs.
 - Target audiences are convinced of the added value of RESILIENCE.

Gameplan

- Agile and goal-oriented approach: adapt to developments and progress made within the RI.
- Implement communication around available services (TNA/RelResearch)/relevant developments/events through existing channels, press releases and free publicity.
- Establish and execute the Action Plan.
- Organize feedback collection after events.
- Organize presentations (Push) on conferences and via personal contacts, emphasizing the added value of the RI.
- Organize collaborative WU CDE Meetings on a regular base.
- For next phase: consider developing a USP campaign.
- For next phase concerning reaching decision makers: organize meetings/roundtables in places where decision makers are (Brussels), create enough time for networking and lobbying.

Resources

- Efforts as in WBS. In descending order: TUA, Uni Sofia, UFO, UNSA, CINECA, WWU, Fscire, Volos, BIU, EPHE, InfAI, KU Leuven, Uni Warsaw.
- In-kind contributions (activities without any efforts in return).
- EU Grant.
- Knowledge on the upcoming services and their status.
- Ability to show the added value and the WHY of RESILIENCE to the stakeholders.
- Draft service catalogue and vision/mission statement.

3.2.1 Involving Professionals in Religious Communities or Churches

The communication strategy does not yet include a strategy to involve professionals in religious communities or churches, and this has to do with the status of the USC and of the project. The strategy to involve professionals in religious communities or churches could include:

- mapping of religious communities and churches in Europe.
- personal approach to professionals working in/for the communities and churches.
- considering targeting specific scholars in the target audience concerning specific services in the catalogue, aiming at interesting them for the services catalogue.
- collecting feedback from the professionals and the impact they see for their community on the concerning results of the RI.
- communicating this impact on religious communities by the RI.

to be developed in the next phase of RESILIENCE under the heading of dissemination.

3.2.2 GLAM Sector

Now that ReIReSearch is open, under certain conditions, for the inclusion of metadata from collections owned by galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM),¹⁸ the message “Make Your Collections Discoverable via ReIReSearch” is relevant. This message can be (and in fact was during PPP) conveyed to GLAM institutions via newsletter, social media and targeted email campaigns. A more elaborate strategy should be developed in the next phase. Preconditions are here: the further update of ReIReSearch, including more collections from partner institutions. In addition to targeted online messages, personal contacts are probably the most important way to achieve cooperation around ReIReSearch. Through personal contacts it can be clarified what efforts are expected from the partner and what benefits presence of collections via ReIReSearch will bring.

3.2.3 Reaching Civil Society

By civil society, that part of society is meant to be organized by and representing citizens in independent foundations, associations etc., promoting social cohesion and strengthening the influence of citizens. In the context of the communication strategy, they are separated from the NGOs. At present, civil society is reached through publications in the media. Ways to reach this target audience in future could include:

- Researchers’ night, inviting wider audiences and discussing themes related to religion and society.
- Religion on site events at cafes and cinemas, with lectures for the wider audience.
- Publications in local, regional or national media.

¹⁸ Deliverable D2.4, Data Management Plan, 21-24.

- Joining civil society events via National Nodes and bringing in the topic of religion/study of religion.
- Collecting addresses of civil society organizations by National Nodes and mapping addresses by RESILIENCE headquarters.

3.3 Communication Strategy Frame for Eastern Europe and The Balkans

No less than five of the 13 RESILIENCE consortium partners¹⁹ are in **Eastern Europe and the Balkans**, namely UFO, UNISOFIA, UNSA, UNIWARSAW²⁰ and VOLOS, which means that RESILIENCE has a special focus on these areas. With regards especially to the Balkans this is important because it reflects the less-known multi-religious and multicultural character of these areas along with the richness and historical value of their traditions, whose heritage still often remains inaccessible to the wider research community.

Partners in Eastern Europe and the Balkans will be faced with specific regional and/or cultural issues. UFO, UNSA, and VOLOS have their own strategy for reaching target audiences and for working on their ambitions. The slightly modified text compared to the strategies in D4.2 are below:

UFO will continue strengthening its role by expanding collaboration with institutions involved in the study of religion and by reaching wider audiences across Albania. Its activities will focus on two local colleges teaching Islamic and Orthodox studies, where UFO will organize open lectures and presentations, making use of RESILIENCE open research data and services. These events will target academic staff and students and will be broadly disseminated through the university's social media channels. UFO will further enhance its networking by engaging with key stakeholders, such as the Albanian Muslim Community, particularly through activities at the newly built Grand Mosque, and by continuing its cooperation with state structures including the State Committee of Cults Albania and the General Directorate of Archives. UFO integrates RESILIENCE objectives into its annual scientific plan, ensuring visibility among researchers, students, and partners in fields such as education, psychology, law, and political sciences.

UNISOFIA will continue its efforts to cooperate with potential partners in Eastern and Central Europe regarding RI-development and upgrade. Therefore, UNISOFIA will efficiently involve a growing group of academics who are engaged in the study of religion, and students as well as young scholars to use the research data and services of RESILIENCE for producing new knowledge. The Bulgarian cultural environment provides a unique opportunity for involving the different religious communities (Orthodox,

¹⁹ Observers and associate partners in these regions participate in communication activities on a voluntary basis and have not been involved in the development of the Communication Strategy for Eastern Europe and the Balkans.

²⁰ WARSAW had to reduce communication activities to a minimum, so that no strategy for this partner is reported.

Catholics, Protestants, Muslims, Jews, Armenians, etc.) in our activities, which UNISOFIA considers as added value to the RESILIENCE Consortium. UNISOFIA will promote the RI in this direction.

UNISOFIA will put emphasis on social media activities to increase the visibility and engagement of RESILIENCE communication channels among Bulgarian followers. Furthermore, UNISOFIA will organize various engagement meetings, including virtual, hybrid, and physical events, with local audiences such as NGOs, experts, and community groups to promote the developing Research Infrastructure on the study of religion. Finally, UNISOFIA's regional activities are being aligned with the broader communication strategy of RESILIENCE and will also involve the use of video production and other advertising materials.

UNSA plans to focus again on physical events and get-togethers. International cooperation between the Faculty of Islamic Studies, Catholic Theological Faculty, Ghazi Husrev Bey's Library of UNSA and similar establishments in the region and beyond is significant. UNSA and its staff are very active both in receiving visitors from abroad and attending events internationally. The plan is to present RESILIENCE at these events whenever feasible. Under normal circumstances there should be at least ten such opportunities every year.

VOLOS continues its efforts to identify potential partners in the region of its responsibility and beyond based on its international networking (e.g. Baltic countries). Volos also aims at reaching a considerable amount of people mainly using social media, regularly sent newsletters, presentations at events, and press releases which will further facilitate the networking of RESILIENCE in the regions under the Volos responsibility. In addition, it will make use of various local media (e.g. non-academic journals, daily newspapers) to approach grassroots people in their respective mother tongue. Finally, it will function as a point of reference / as an entrance point for those from Eastern and Central Europe (Greece itself included) who would like to join the RI and use its services and network for research. For this purpose, Pull communication tools like face-to-face collaboration, presentations, feedback collection, social media interaction, etc., will be used.

In collaboration with UFO, UNISOFIA, UNSA, and VOLOS, the following updated version of the Communication Strategy Frame for Eastern Europe and the Balkans was developed. One of the main updates concerns the impression of the external situation, which seems to be improved. Was there first the belief that stakeholders are not always convinced of the necessity of a RI for the study of religion, the situation is now regarded that, depending on the context, stakeholders can be convinced of the necessity of a RI for the study of religion. Besides, the estimate currently is that audiences are interested in services that are up and running.

NB. The above strategy is minimally updated compared to the Communication Strategy for Eastern Europe and The Balkans as described in D4.2.²¹ New is the reference of UNISOFIA to the use of video production and other advertising materials. It should be considered if the KPIs for the next phase should be updated in this respect too.

²¹ D4.2, Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan, p. 26-30.

Internal situation

- RESILIENCE as the RI for Religious Studies is moving towards full operation.

Vision

- RESILIENCE connects research centers, data holders and services distributed all over Europe, and creates new instruments and services for its scientific community.
- RESILIENCE facilitates faster, better, and more efficient research as well as access to online and physical sources. It offers a central place where to find evolving tools and big data.
- RESILIENCE enters the field of new developments of DH, offering FAIR access to data and storing data, as well as to resources, tools etc.

Accountability

- AU-UFO co-organizes events with religious communities and expands cooperation with state structures.
- AU-UFO encourages academics from Kosovo and North-Macedonia to take part in events.
- UNSA organizes events/personal meetings/face to face meetings.
- VOLOS puts an emphasis on webinars, on social media, videos, podcasts, newsletters, press releases and publications in media.
- AU-UFO, UNSA, UNISOFIA and VOLOS monitor and collect statistics. 10 presentations in B&H.
- UniSofia organises research events with participants from different religious communities and promotes RI for Religious Studies.
- TUA monitors the KPI scores.
- WU CDE supports the above by announcing, redistribution of news, supplying of materials, means, etc.

Stakeholders

- Internal: WU CDE members
- Target Audiences: Academics, Non-academics (Religious Community, NGO's), Decision makers, New partners, Media (and general public in Albania and Greece).

External situation

- Depending on their context, stakeholders can be convinced of the necessity of a RI for the study on religion.
- Decision makers in the region do not always see the necessity of doing research on religion.

Ambition

- In 2026:**
- RESILIENCE is recognized in Europe and beyond as a unique and indispensable RI.
 - Target audiences in Eastern Europe and the Balkans are aware of the RI and its services, and take part in or co-organize events.
 - Target audiences are convinced of the added value of RESILIENCE.
 - Target audiences are aware of the relevance of religious phenomena in the specified area, especially in Albania.

Gameplan

- Communication is aimed at informing and influencing (two way communication), and encouraging dialogue. Interaction is key.
- Informing, influencing, and interaction will take place during webinars, physical events, get-togethers and personal contacts.
- One-way communication is being done through various touch points.
- In presentations the relevance of a RI for Eastern Europe and The Balkans is made clear.
- Check continuously if key messages take into consideration the agile approach: there is no one size fits all.

Resources

- Efforts as in WBS.
- In-kind contributions.
- EU Grant.
- Personal/institutions contacts with interested communities/institutions.
- Competence to show the WHY of the RI to the specific target audience, taking into account the situation it is in.

3.4 Dissemination Strategy Frame for Services

The dissemination “lite” strategy is included, focusing on the current USC. In a subsequent phase, this services strategy can then be converted into a separate and more focused strategy. It is advisable to also consider the recommendations and options for publicizing services from D4.4., the Study on a Subset of Services.

Internal Situation

- A first version of the services catalogue is available, containing a list of titles, descriptions, and links to partner websites.
- A measurement system concerning the uptake cannot be applied yet.

Vision

- RESILIENCE connects research centers, data holders and services distributed all over Europe and creates new instruments and services for its scientific community.
- RESILIENCE offers direct, fast and effective access to its services..

Accountability

- WU CDE (TUA) sees to sufficient publicity and process management. KU Leuven will support this, and deliver content.
- KPI June 2026 100 clicks by individual website visitors on services page on RESILIENCE website (to be developed Jan/ Feb 2026).

Stakeholders

- Internal: WU CDE members.
- External: archetypes as defined by WU Users.
- Target Audiences: Academics, Non-academics (Religious Community, NGO's, civil society), Decision makers, New partners, Media.

External Situation

- Users are insufficiently aware of the possibilities offered by the services catalogue. However, they may be aware of it through press releases distributed December 2025.

Ambition

- Target audiences are aware of services in the services catalogue.

Gameplan

- Agile and goal-oriented approach: adapt to developments in WU Services.
- Lite campaign Jan/May 2026, highlighting the service categories.
- Inclusion in general PPT.
- Web presence (page with categories/per category a list of services).
- Monthly newsitem 2026 on services catalogue (website/ newsletter/social media).

Resources

- Budget for website development.
- Efforts WU CDE Team and especially TUA
- Services catalogue.
- Knowledge about further development services catalogue at KUL.
- Expertise of KUL and service providers

3.5 Social Media Strategy

A social media strategy is included in the communication strategy frames, because our news is not only disseminated through the website and newsletter, but also through our social media channels. The Action Plan can be regarded as, and functions as a social media content calendar, since all relevant scheduled actions are expected to be shared on social media too. The Action Plan also includes the planned data of deliverables, which gives the team the opportunity to generate news based on publications and share it via social media. Strategic and operational use of the RESILIENCE social media channels can be found in the previously developed Guide for Social Media and Online Collaboration, accessible via the project repository.²²

During the period under review the “Voices” series was continued, asking people to reflect on questions related to our work building the research infrastructure, both via blogs and videos. Besides, emphasis has been placed on posting photos and texts related to TNA fellowship stays. These posts often generate positive responses and engagement. In view of the imminent publication of the services catalogue in M42, the series “In our service catalogue,” which was based on the preliminary version of the catalogue, has been discontinued. The USC is expected to provide more than enough input to be distributed via the RESILIENCE channels during the remaining months of the PPP.

The social media matrix below provides an overview of how to reach our target groups via the various touchpoints.

3.5.1 Social Media Matrix

Touchpoint	Main Audience	Type of Content	Tone of Voice
Facebook	Partners, Academics, Non-Academics	Project updates, RESILIENCE at work content, visuals, series. Engagements/asking questions	Inspirational
LinkedIn	Partners, Academics, Non-Academics, Decision makers, Media	Project updates, RESILIENCE at work content, networking evidence, visuals, sharing expertise. Engagements/asking questions.	Professional
X	Partners, Academic, Non-Academic, Decision makers, Media	Project updates, short posts, visuals, series.	Friendly, humorous

²² See link in the attachment 3 (Links to RESILIENCE living documents in the project repository).

Touchpoint	Main Audience	Type of Content	Tone of Voice
		Engagements/asking questions.	
Instagram	Broad public	Project updates, photos, reels, RESILIENCE at work content, stories, visuals, series	
YouTube	Partners, Academic, Non-Academic	Project updates, photos, reels, RESILIENCE at work content, stories, visuals, series	Professional, inspirational

Table 2 Social Media Matrix

3.6 Key Performance Indicators

Key performance indicators have been set for this phase (up to and including May 2026) and are monthly reviewed. An overview of the KPIs and the results achieved can be found in Attachment 1. An update of the KPIs is foreseen in the next version of the CDEP, in accordance with the targets set at that time.

4 From D4.2 to D4.3: Progress and Outlook

4.1 Introduction

As the Grant Agreement indicates, “the development of the services catalogues, the implementation of the user strategy and the objective of the construction of the ERIC, the impact measurement methodology as well as other expected outcomes of the PP require adjustments and improvements of this plan”,²³ regular updates of the communication and dissemination plans following the progress made by the consortium are essential.

The outcomes mentioned above were the reason for disseminating news and adjusting the various strategies, particularly about the target groups and messages. At the same time, progress in building the RI and the concrete results thereof have always been a reason to keep target groups informed of this progress, as evidenced, for example, by the number of posts on social media, the website, and the number of newsletters (see Report WP4 Statistics M1-M41 in the appendix).

In this chapter more detailed information concerning progress focusing on various aspects of the operational work is presented, whereas also future perspectives are included, thus providing an outlook to the next phase of the RI.

4.2 Publication of Foundational Deliverables

Concerning the above-mentioned outcomes, following foundational deliverables were published in M42: the Statutes and Technical Description of the research infrastructure (D1.2), the User Services Catalogue (D2.2), Workshop Proceedings 2nd Batch (D3.2), the Documented Use Cases 2nd Batch (D3.4) and the Impact Analysis (D5.1). These have been reflected upon from a communication and dissemination perspective, resulting in the following:²⁴

Statutes and Technical Description of the research infrastructure (D1.2)

- The deliverable is a helpful document, containing relevant information for convincing our target audiences of the necessity of a research infrastructure for the study of religion (Generic Strategic Communication Goal 2) and for addressing especially the target audience of policy makers and governmental organisations. With this in mind, the message for policymakers in the communication

²³ Deliverable D5.3 of RESILIENCE’s Design Phase.

²⁴ The assumption here is that RESILIENCE will transition to another phase at the end of the PPP. Whether this will be the case, and what phase that will be, is not yet known at this time. See also the reservation made by D1.2 itself, stating that “at the end of the RESILIENCE PPP RESILIENCE will not be able to submit the ERIC proposal”, p 4.

matrix (table 1) has been adjusted. A more elaborated strategy is to be described in the next version of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan.

User Services Catalogue (D2.2)

- The availability of this catalogue offers a great opportunity to substantiate our vision and mission with concrete examples, see par. 2.3 where the Message Houses are presented. The launch of the catalogue in December 2025 was accompanied by the distribution of a press release to relevant target groups, while a (social media) campaign is also being prepared for the remaining months of the PPP together with a web presentation of the services, which can be shown until an official RESILIENCE Portal is available.

Workshop Proceedings 2nd Batch (D3.2) and Documented Use Cases 2nd Batch (D3.4)

- RESILIENCE places its users at the heart of its mission, ensuring that all services are tailored to their needs, expectations, and visions. The publication of these two deliverables offer opportunities for further facilitating feedback loops, see par. 4.6.4 of D4.3. Besides, the refinement of the user needs should in the next phase be used to update the communication matrix when it comes to description of the needs of the target audiences and the subsequent messages from RESILIENCE.

Impact Analysis (D5.1)

- Deliverable D5.1 analyzes and showcases the impact the operational research infrastructure will have on various target audiences. It shows how RESILIENCE will support scientific excellence, digital innovation, cultural heritage, social inclusion and evidence-based policymaking. The content of this deliverable offers many starting points for working on communication objectives and refining our messages in terms of how services create change²⁵. A separate webpage on impact is published, while the possibilities for effectively bringing the content to the attention of our target groups can be further investigated. The deliverable contains valuable information and argumentation that can be used for communication and dissemination purposes and included in future strategies. Referred is to chapter 8 of this document, to which it should be added that a further update of the communication matrix can be addressed, whereby argumentation in D5.1 is transferred into needs

²⁵ RESILIENCE PPP Deliverable D5.1, p. 7.

of target audiences and messages of the RI in this respect. Moreover, paragraph P13,²⁶ dealing with communication and outreach, should be integrated in future strategies.²⁷

4.3 Focal Points²⁸

What	Work done	Result
1. The user's archetypes and a different strategy to reach out especially to scholars (with WP Users)	Contact WP2 in various months.	Completed, see D4.2, p. 35 and D4.3, par. 2.3.
2. Refining the methodology to evaluate the impact of Communication & Dissemination Activities (with WP Impact)	Internal discussions.	Common agreement, that given the nature of impact (effect on the long term) it is not possible to evaluate it in the current phase. The publication of D5.1 will shed new light on this, to be further elaborated in the next phase of the project. See D4.3, par. 8.
3. Tailoring the Communication & Dissemination Plan according to different religious/cultural/social contexts.	Internal discussions.	Tailoring to different religious and cultural contexts has been achieved by working with the geographic preconditions (D4.1, page 14/15), which are also incorporated into the various partner matrices (Appendix D4.2), combined with working with the Golden Circle model or Simon Sinek (par. 2.7). Adaptation to different social contexts is not (yet) on the agenda due to the lack of an operational services catalogue, ready for uptake.
4. Understanding the terms of an exploitation strategy for the RI.	Desktop study, internal discussions.	Completed in D4.2., see chapter 7.
5. Addressing the issue of KPIs for the specific RESILIENCE RI: typology and measurement methodology.	Desktop study, internal discussions.	Completed in D4.2, appendix and D4.2, appendix (stakeholder KPIs). See also fn. 8 of Attachment 1 of D4.3.
6. Improving the public representation and public image of the RI.	Internal discussions.	The public representation is constantly under review and update. A study answering the question of how target audiences see RESILIENCE and what measures can be taken to solve the discrepancy between perceived image and identity is in planning, see par. 7.2.1.
7. Ensuring a more effective connection to civil society and the private sector.	Internal discussion, consulting other	The connection to civil society and the private sector will be realized in the IP through activities such as

²⁶ This pathway focuses on how RIs connect with society—by sharing knowledge, raising awareness, and making their work visible and meaningful beyond academia. In studies of religion, this includes engaging the public through media, exhibitions, public talks, or online platforms—helping people better understand religion's role in culture and society, and showing how research can promote dialogue, inclusion, and mutual understanding (D5.1, p. 27).

²⁷ Due to time constraints this exercise could not be carried out for D4.3.

²⁸ See RESILIENCE PPP Grant Agreement 18/08/2022, DOA, p. 9

What	Work done	Result
	communication/dissemination plans.	special events, co-organization of events, publications, lectures, exhibitions and media appearances. The private sector comes into the picture as soon as steps are taken toward exploitation. This could include bringing in publishing houses. See also D4.3, par. 3.2.3. To be included in the next update of the CDEP.
8. Taking into consideration the specific needs of different academic communities in dissemination actions.	Internal discussions.	Completed in D4.1, D4.2 and D4.3 (see communication matrix, table 1, which is regularly under review).
9. Working on a more defined communication about how RESILIENCE contributes to the skills of its users.	Internal discussion.	Updated set of specific messages (par 2.5).

Table 3 Follow Up of Focal Points according to GA

4.4 Tasks

What	Work done	Result
10. Work on internal communication related to the views within the consortium about the RI itself and specific services like ReReSearch before putting in place a PULL approach.	Internal discussions.	Completed in D4.2, p.37. Change in opinion about using the Pull approach, see task 12.c.
11. Discuss the recommendation of the ESFRI reviewers December 2021 and try to incorporate them in the upcoming version of D5.3 (2022): Take into consideration the specific needs of different academic communities in future dissemination actions for the RESILIENCE infrastructure (Recommendation 11 of the current CDP).	Internal discussions.	Completed in D4.2, par. 4.1, point 8 and the updated communication matrix (table 1) in D4.3.
12. Discuss [internal] recommendations 1-10 ²⁹ as described in the current CDP [=	Internal discussions, desktop study.	Partly completed in D4.1.D4.1 left 6 recommendations, see below.

²⁹ Recommendation 1-10 from D5.3 RESILIENCE Design Phase incorporated into D4.1.

What	Work done	Result
D5.3 RESILIENCE Design Phase] and take measures that will secure inclusion in the updated version(s) of the CDP.		
12.a Recommendation 1 Develop a Strategy to Connect with Other European Projects and RIs for the Preparatory Phase.	Internal alignment.	Connect with other European Projects and RIs through personal contacts, mainly of (executive) directors.
12.b Recommendation 2 Formulate a brand promise for the various target audiences, including the roots of the brand and the wings of the brand. Roots are the functional mark promise and brands the emotional mark promise. For example: "RESILIENCE makes the newest tools and instruments available, so that you can become the best scholar (cf. Van Liemt/Koot, 231).	Internal discussion.	The marketing approach, including the brand promise, the roots and the wings, was abandoned during the PPP due to the status of the USC, which purports to be an overview of what is available from the partners. It is possible that this approach will be revisited in the future. Meanwhile, the message houses (fig. 1 and fig. 2) are an alternative.
12.c Recommendation 3 Check with the target audiences if the brand promise is relevant, distinctive and credible. Regarding the Push and Pull approach (see par. 3.2.2) RESILIENCE is focusing on strengthening the Pull effect of its approach. To achieve that aim, the feedback of the partners will be used.	Internal discussion.	The marketing approach, including the brand promise, the roots and the wings, was abandoned during the PPP due to the status of the USC, which purports to be an overview of what is available from the partners. It is possible that this approach will be revisited in the future. Meanwhile, the message houses (fig. 1 and fig. 2) are an alternative.
12.d Recommendation 4 Organize a brainstorming meeting with RESILIENCE partners about their experiences with Pull related actions (like presence in the media and attending workshops and conferences) and discuss best practices. Implement these best practices in the updated version(s) of the CDP. Discuss also the	Internal discussion.	This recommendation is obsolete, see 12.a, 12.b and 12.c. It was decided in M9 to work with the Golden Circle instead, see par. 1.2. A sample test with 3 people from each target audience to see if the brand promise is relevant planned in M40 is obsolete, because it is be implemented via the identity vs image study, see D4.3 par. 7.2.1

What	Work done	Result
content of the communication and dissemination activities: how can we better show the added value of RESILIENCE, so that target audiences will act as leaders instead of targets?		
12.e Recommendation 5 Stay in close contact with service developers. Once a basic version or even full version is available, actively engage in communications to reach the target audiences.	Ongoing communication activities.	Posts and website items on especially TNA, RelReSeach and Zenodo.
13. Discuss the recommendation of the ESFRI reviewers December 2021 and try to incorporate them in D4.2. Take into consideration the specific needs of different academic communities in future dissemination actions for the RESILIENCE infrastructure.	Internal discussions, desktop study.	Completed, see D4.3, task 11.
14. Discuss the evaluation of the EC reviewers December 2023 as described in the paragraph on the criterion impact and take measures that will secure inclusion in the updated version(s) of the CDP.	Internal discussions, desktop study.	Completed, see D4.2, par. 3.5.
15. Define the differentiated strategy to reach out to the RESILIENCE users archetypes and especially to scholars	Discussed with the WP3 team if archetypes fit into the target groups.	Completed, see D4.3, par. 4.1 point 1.
16. Consult with institutions that already developed best practises in the field of communicating religious related topics (e.g. curators of religious heritage).	Desktop study and personal contacts.	Completed, see D4.2, p. 39.
17. Exploit the network of the RelReS TNA grant holders to gain insights on how to (better) communicate the results of the RESILIENCE TNA Programme.	Online meeting with RelReS TNA grant-holders in M5.	Completed, see D4.2, p. 39.
18. Organise face to face meetings in collaboration with the WP USERS with selected target audiences in order to get a deeper insight into their needs and how to improve their skills, as well as their image of the RI.	Internal discussions and alignment of the work.	Completed, see D4.2, p. 39 and D4.3, par. 6.1.

What	Work done	Result
19. Update and implement the RESILIENCE C&D Plan, facilitate, stimulate and monitor the activities planned	The tracking file, regular monitoring and action plan are supporting this.	Completed/ongoing.
20. Define roles and responsibilities of the participating partners and other partners willing to contribute to the implementation.	Ongoing discussions.	Completed, see page 40 of D4.2
21. Propose a strategy for the exploitation of RESILIENCE results.	Desktop study and internal discussions.	Completed, see chapter 7 of D4.2.
22. Develop new or updated communication means like flyers, banners etc.	Ongoing activity.	Completed, specified in D4.3, par. 6. 8.
23. Elaborate a green approach to communication meetings, ensuring alternatives to physical meetings	Internal alignment.	Completed, see D4.1, p. 113, 114, 115.
24. Support WP SUSTAINABILITY in all communication activities aiming at the establishment of the ERIC and alignment of national strategies and adopt a dedicated communication strategy aiming at establishing new partnerships with academic and non-academic data holders.	Internal discussions.	Completed, see D4.2, p. 40.

Table 4 Follow Up of Tasks According to GA

4.5 Advice Reviewers ³⁰

What	Work done	Result
25. Work with living documents and keep better track of progress.	Ongoing updating of documents.	Updated living documents in project repository, accessible to reviewers. See D4.3, attachment 3.
26. Make KPIs more quantifiable	Updating of KPIs for the whole project period in	Completed, see page 41 of D4.2

³⁰ See general project review consolidated reports 07/11/2023 and 12/02/2025.

	alignment with the developments so far. Decision to prepare a 6-month report of key results. update the monitoring/reporting system supported by Google Data Studio.	
27. Avoid pushing forward writing the Impact and Exploitation chapters in the Communication/Dissemination/Exploitation plan	Decision to include first versions in D4.2 and final versions in D4.3. Study of the topic, alignment with the CDE Team.	In progress. D4.3 shows updates in par. 8; however, this chapter needs further robustness. To be carried out in the next phase. Work in the next phase will probably also include a separate WP on Exploitation.
28. Report EC based on review October 2023 inviting the team to define more quantifiable and measurable KPIs for each of the stakeholders	Internal discussion.	Completed, see par. 3.5 of D4.2.
29. RESILIENCE could more efficiently develop the digital tools and online advertising, yet the social media and digital dissemination are at this time not yet developed as much as they could.	Internal discussion.	Ongoing. Increased use of videos/reels on social media, for example: Number of videos on FB M1-M27 (27 months): 29. Number of videos on FB M28-M40 (13 months): 26. Social media monitoring takes place through the collection of statistics. There are also plans for a social media campaign following the publication of the USC. This will be further developed in a subsequent phase of the project.
30. Review Report February 2025: Some actors are defined somewhat broadly (e.g., "civil society"?), and the general categorization proposed in deliverable D4.2 is more or less unified but would have benefited from more depth by considering national variations regarding the question of religions in society and in the academic world, as well as the interest of public authorities in the study of religions: does the European issue of "diversity" arise in the same way everywhere? (see D4.2).	Internal discussion.	The result of the internal discussion is that individual presenters should work with Sinek's Golden Circle Model, page 14 of D4.2, customizing the messages themselves to the different target audiences. Besides, a clearer description of civil society and how to approach this target group in future when RESILIENCE has become the ERIC status has been added to D4.3, see par. 3.2.3.
31. Feedback Better balance the methodologies for collecting and processing feedback from the various terrains.	Internal discussion.	Updated evaluation form, asking respondents to indicate the disciplines they are working in.

32. Feedback: Strategies can benefit more from feedback processes.	Internal discussion.	WP4 facilitates evaluation of events, starting from proposing an evaluation, drafting evaluation forms and collecting data on the level of satisfaction and impressions of participants to report on the results and disseminating the reports among relevant internal groups. Collecting and evaluating feedback from communication and dissemination activities should be taken up in the next phase.
33. Feedback: Filter information coming from feedback by differentiating according to career status and familiarity with the RI.	Internal discussion.	Elaborated evaluation form, asking for the status of career and familiarity with the RI of respondents. See D4.3, par. 6.1.3.
34. Finally, the communication plan shows that the strategy is facing limits (quantitative results are not always convincing through social media and mainstream media. There is a need for deeper reflection on the types of media and their relevance in the overall strategy (D4.1).	Internal discussion (meeting 25/02/2025).	Ongoing. Encouragement to be more proactive and responsive on social media, see also D4.3 par. 3.5. Inviting mainstream media for events and encouraging contacts between TNA fellows/journalists (in updated TNA communication workflow 02.00). Defining additional KPIs for publications in traditional media. Scheduling actions in Action Plan.
35. The expressed desire to expand to GLAM is commendable but requires a more specific strategy.	Internal discussions, desktop study.	In progress, see D4.3, par. 3.2.2.
36. Encourage Awareness vision/mission statement among consortium partner institutions	Internal discussion.	Completed. All participants inform internally about the progress made, in any form, be it during regular meetings, via newsletters etc. It is advised to especially communicate the why (vision/mission) and not only the what (results and updates). NB. Future reminders are included in the Action Plan.

Table 5 Follow up of Advice Reviewers

4.6 RESILIENCE Updates

4.6.1 Operational

When implementing the strategies, the need for updates on the operational level became apparent regarding:

What	Work done	Result
37. Update press contact list in GLAM section.	Collection of email addresses, added to press contact list.	Extended press contact list with emails of GLAM section institutions. The list will be expanded further in the future.
38. Desire to reconsider attendance at X and to decide on this in M44.	Internal discussion, online review.	Participation on X has pros (reach, specific target groups as well as EC institutions well represented, easy to handle) and cons (declining trust, increasing advertising, universities and other Ris have suspended/deleted their accounts). The decision is to remain on X for the time being to keep our followers, to be moderately active, to evaluate once a year or in case of new developments.
39. Develop a strategy/make a plan for reaching civil society in the coming years.	Internal discussion (WU CDE Meeting 25/02/2025).	See par. 3.2.3 of D4.3 Besides, mapping of think tanks on research and religion in different countries, like Theos in the UK could be done.

Table 6 Updates on Operational Level

4.6.2 Monitoring and Reporting

During RESILIENCE's PPP, monitoring was constantly done, resulting in following reporting:

- Reporting M1-M4 for D4.1.
- Reporting M1-M12 for upload in the EC Portal.
- Reporting M13-M18, internal.
- Reporting M19-24, internal.
- Reporting M13-30, internal.
- Reporting M1-M36, internal.
- Reporting M1-M27 for D4.2.
- Reporting M1-M41 for D4.3.

These reports were produced for various reasons. First and foremost, to gain and guarantee insight into progress and results. In addition, due to obligations to the EC and to provide reviewers with insight into developments via the living documents. Finally, because of internal guidelines to prepare semi-annual

reports during the first half of the PPP. The reports were evaluated each time and provided with recommendations, which were implemented as much as possible. Monitoring and reporting have thus become an integral part of the CDE work.

4.6.3 TNA Programme Communication Workflow

The TNA Programme Communication workflow, a document describing the end-to-end process that helps teams achieve their goals by connecting the right people to the right data at the right time, was updated by giving the TNA hosts more responsibility for securing content to be disseminated and for arranging contacts with journalists.³¹

4.6.4 Feedback Loops

The collection of feedback and the sharing and use of the feedback is facilitated and encouraged by WP4. In practical terms, this means that, in close collaboration with the organizer of a RESILIENCE event, WP4 considers the right questions that can help gain insight into the extent to which participants feel that the defined goals have been achieved. This consideration leads to an appropriate and goal-oriented online evaluation form that the organizer presents to participants after an event, such as a brainstorming meeting or workshop. WP4 processes the results into an overview, with the organization providing the analysis, conclusions, and recommendations. The final report, including the recommendations, is distributed within the consortium. The organizer is asked to share the report with the participants.

A more general form of feedback collection has also been considered due to the user-centered approach and the final product offered for this purpose in the Preparatory Phase. This could involve collecting responses from respondents who were previously approached for feedback (work carried out by WP3) on the current version of the User Services Catalog (D2.2). Considerations include what has been explained in the service strategy, namely that the user needs “are relevant to both the central hub and the National Nodes and can be used as a guideline to prioritise activities in proposals and plan the service development for the IP”,³² indicating clearly that the alignment will only be fully developed in the next phase. For the time being, the planned Core Services will match the user needs, whereas the Community Services presented in the USC mainly refer to what is already available among the partners, rather than aiming at matching the outcome of our interactions with researchers in the study of religion. In RESILIENCE’s ERIC status, the National Nodes will be responsible for meeting the user needs.³³

³¹ See Attachment 3 in the Appendix (confidential).

³² Deliverable D2.1, Services and Implementation Strategy, accessible via https://www.resilience-ri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/RESILIENCE_WP2_D2.1_Services-Preparation-and-Implementation-Strategy_03.00_FINAL.pdf

³³ Deliverable D2.2, User Services Catalogue, p. 9: “Future expansion of the community services will be coordinated by the National Nodes based on our community’s needs.” Deliverable D2.1 is accessible via https://www.resilience-ri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/RESILIENCE_WP2_D2.2_UserServicesCatalogue_02.00_FINAL.pdf.

Once the overview of services is visualized on RESILIENCE's website, a more general review could be carried out. Another option could be to wait for the HORTUS³⁴ version of the catalogue and then get back to the respondents of previous meetings and queries. For the moment a decision was not made, postponing it to the next phase of RESILIENCE.

4.6.5 Updates of Strategies

All strategies in this deliverable should be reviewed in the next phase from the perspective of the status of the services catalogue development. Here a reference is suitable for the valuable recommendations made by WP Services in D2.1 for the role of National Nodes,³⁵ which could be supported by RESILIENCE's Headquarters in a more general sense and from the principle of subsidiarity (par. 8.3 of this document):

- Facilitate interaction and collaboration on services between the institutions and other local actors in the country.
- Engage with the local community and communicate on the progress, opportunities and engagement activities of the RI. Collect feedback from the local network to serve as input for the RI strategy at the European level.
- Widen the communication on RI activities and services to the broader community more indirectly related to RS research.
- Engage with policy makers to ensure national/regional commitments for the investment aimed at strengthening the RI through the national node contribution and shared facilities.
- Seek alignment with other national RI consortia such as DARIAH, CLARIN and CESSDA to ensure optimal collaboration, reuse of tools, data and services, and sharing of expertise to stimulate cooperation and prevent duplication.³⁶

³⁴ For Hortus see Deliverable D2.1, p. 30.

³⁵ The National Node is here perceived as an organizational entity that functions as a national liaison and brings together relevant national stakeholders in the country in a systematic way.

³⁶ Deliverable D2.1, p. 25, accessible via [RESILIENCE WP2 D2.1 Services-Preparation-and-Implementation-Strategy_03.00_FINAL.pdf](#)

5 Action Plan M28-M44

The actions scheduled for M28-M44 as listed in the online Action Plan can be found in the appendix.

6 Main Results and Achievements

In this chapter the main results and achievements are presented concerning the website, social media and newsletter performances, the events organized by RESILIENCE, TNA Dissemination, RESILIENCE's contacts with societies and other Ris, the development of communication and dissemination materials, and last but not least the dissemination possibilities coming from the publication of the User Services Catalogue and Data Management Plan. Highlights from these results and achievements are presented in chapter 7.

6.1 Website

The website www.resilience.ri.eu, the most important communication and dissemination tool, has performed well. This is evident, among other things, from the content output M1-M41: 228 posts (KPI 200) and the audience growth: 28.278 active users (KPI 20.000). Session quality is high with an average session duration of 3:56 (KPI: 2:00), 1.079 sessions/month (KPI 800) and 3.598 page views/month (KPI 2500). Pages related to the TNA programme show steady engagement and attract a significant number of users. The "Call for Applications" page recorded 3.071 visitors. TNA applications significantly exceed KPI (93 vs 30), which is a major success.

6.2 Social Media

The social media presence is steadily growing. LinkedIn (522 followers; KPI 500) and YouTube (153 subscribers; KPI 150) have exceeded end-project KPIs. All engagement KPIs have already been achieved, except for Facebook. During the reporting period M1-M41, the project reached 207.143 people via the social media channels of all partners and RESILIENCE, which represents significant growth compared to the previous reporting period (M1-27: 112.605 people. 96.837 people were reached via the RESILIENCE social media channels (M1-M27: 54.557).

6.3 Newsletter

Newsletter engagement, despite lagging subscriber numbers, is excellent (43.13% open rate and 11,06 click rate (vs KPIs of 30% and 5%). The total number of newsletters distributed M1-M41 (37 vs KPI 24), each containing approximately 5-6 news items, shows that there has always been sufficient news to share with the target audience.

6.4 Total Reach

The statistics report shows that all consortium partners together reached 552.467 people with their communications during the reporting period. Applying 10% overlap percentage to this figure gives a total number of people reached of 470.220, an excellent result considering the end-of-project KPI of 500.000 people reached.

6.5 Event Evaluation M30-M43³⁷

As stated in par. 4.6.4, for each RESILIENCE event an online evaluation form is prepared, asking respondents about their experiences considering the previously set goal for the participants. In addition, an overall impression is asked, rating from 1 (lowest score) to 10 (highest score). The evaluation form is offered to the participants as soon as possible after event closing, or even at the end of the event. The results are collected and reported, whereby the reports are shared within the consortium and if possible, with the event participants.

Nr.	Description	M	Nr. of participants	Nr. of respondents	Type of audience (internal/external) ³⁸	General Score Goal Achievement ³⁹	Overall impression ⁴⁰
15 ⁴¹	Training Prototype, Rome: Religion for the Senses. How to Read, Treat and Hear Religious Sources	34	12	10	I/E	Good	8,2
16	RESILIENCE Workshop WP3 @University of Münster	36	9	9	I	Good	8,1
17	Training Prototype "AI for Religious Studies – Automatic Keyword Tagging of Multimedia Data"	36	12	8	I	Good	7,6
18	Roundtable Religion and the EU, Brussels	36	45	Not evaluated	E	-	-
19	RESILIENCE Sponsored PhD Forum at	38	25	Not evaluated	E	-	-

³⁷ See for event evaluation M1-M29 Deliverable D4.2, p.45.

³⁸ Internal means: affiliated with a RESILIENCE partner, not necessarily belonging to the core-team.

³⁹ Rating: Poor, Satisfactory, Good, Very Good (Likert-scale). The social-desirability bias was not checked specifically. However, by asking questions that are as objective as possible, an attempt has been made to prevent this bias.

⁴⁰ Rating on a range from 1-10, whereby 10 is the highest score.

⁴¹ Events 1-14 have been reported in D4.2.

Nr.	Description	M	Nr. of participants	Nr. of respondents	Type of audience (internal/external) ³⁸	General Score Goal Achievement ³⁹	Overall impression ⁴⁰
	#EuARE2025						
20	Religion and Business: a Good Match? RESILIENCE Sponsored Roundtable at #EuARE2025	38	20	Not evaluated	E	-	-
21	Religious Freedom: Evident Yet Complicated, RESILIENCE Supported Roundtable at #EuARE2025	38	10	Not evaluated	E	-	-
22.	Workshop "Shaping the Future of Research on Religion through RESILIENCE RI"	41	25	9	I	Good	9

Table 7 Results Event Evaluation by Participants

6.5.1 General Score Goal Achievement According to Participants

Each evaluation form tested the extent to which participants felt that the goals defined for them in advance had been achieved, using a Likert scale. The Likert scale was divided into: Poor, Satisfactory, Good and Very Good. Previously, these four options were chosen because with an odd number there is a tendency to choose the middle option. By offering only four options, respondents are challenged to take a clear position. However, the disadvantage of using a Likert scale is that it is difficult to calculate an average. To do this, the method chosen for the three events mentioned above was to assign several points to each option - namely 1 for Poor, 2 for Satisfactory, 3 for Good and 4 for Very Good - and then divide the total by the number of questions and that number by the number of respondents. This results in a score between 1 and 4, showing where this final score comes closest to:

- Poor 1
- Satisfactory 2
- Good 3
- Very good 4

Applying this to the four events mentioned above results in the following calculation leads to the results below, giving a more precise result than included in table 7:⁴²

Event Nr.	Total score goal achievement	Nr. of questions	Number of respondents	Total score goal achievement divided by number of questions	Total score previous column divided by number of respondents
15	281	10	10	28,1	2,8
16	149	5	9	29,8	3,3
17	205	6	10	34,2	3,4
22	247	9	10	27,4	2,7
Total	882	30	39	119,5	3
Average	220,5	7,5	9,8	29,4	3⁴³

Table 8 Average Total Score Goal Achievement According to Event Participants

The average score according to the respondents to the goal achievement is a convincing **Good (3)**, according to the above explained methodology.

⁴² Event evaluation of RESILIENCE organized sessions at the European Academy of Religions annual conference are not in the table, because practically it is not achievable collecting evaluations from the participants.

⁴³ Minimal deviations due to rounding to one decimal place are possible.

6.5.2 Average Score Events Rating

Figure 3 Overall Impression Participants RESILIENCE Events M1-M41

Fig. 3 shows that, in general, the events organized by RESILIENCE receive high ratings from the respondents. On a scale of 1-10, the average rating for the events evaluated - which were all asked to be rated on a scale of 1-10 - is even **8,4**. Evaluation reports are constantly shared within the consortium, provided with recommendations for organizing future events. Recommendations focus on issues such as time management and didactic aspects, also on a goal-oriented approach and content-related aspects. The living document of the collected recommendations is accessible to all team members.

6.5.3 Status of Career and Familiarity with the RI

Respondents of the events 15, 16, 17 and 22 have additionally been asked about their status of career and familiarity with the RI:

Figure 4 Familiarity with the RI of Event Participants (Respondents)

Figure 5 Status of Career of Event Participants (Respondents)

6.5.4 Conclusion Event Evaluation

The survey results show very favorable outcomes in terms of the extent to which respondents feel that the objectives were achieved and in terms of overall satisfaction with the event. There are hardly any exceptions to this, from which it can be concluded that RESILIENCE organizes meaningful events for its participants.

⁴⁴ The familiarity with the RI was not checked for event 17.

Because only four evaluations check the variables “Status of Career” and “Familiarity with the RI”, there is currently too little data to compare the results of the degree of satisfaction or, for example, the achievement of the objectives with these variables. If questions related to status of career and familiarity with the RI are included in the evaluation forms as standard, a correlation analyses should be conducted in the future.

It is also advisable to investigate exactly why the event rating is so positive, for example, which aspect it relates to. Finally, it is advisable to systematically include the degree of satisfaction of the organizers and the extent to which they consider their objectives to have been achieved in a separate evaluation form for organizers, so that this can also be used for management purposes.

6.6 TNA Dissemination

TNA Dissemination worked extremely well as presented in par. 7.1.2. Besides, initial steps have been taken to reach the broader target group of civil society through the media, by bringing TNA scholars in contact with journalists. WU CDE has made the TNA team proposals in this respect for 10 scholars who were expected to enjoy their research stay because of the third call. However, in practice it appeared difficult to establish contacts between TNA scholars and journalists. For the next phase it should be considered to continue, or to think of another approach highlighting the relevance of the study on religion for today’s issues in regional or national media.

6.7 Societies

Following the internal meeting of the WP and WU leaders November 13, 2024, and the meeting with the Advisory Board on November 14/15, 2024, in Bologna, contact has been sought with societies relating religion to other disciplines such as sociology, philosophy, law and medicine. Email addresses have been added to the press contact list, whereas social media connections have been made. In addition, several dozen contacts from societies were approached by email, and further discussions were held with some of them in person. No concrete agreements for cooperation have been made at this stage, but the network has expanded as a result.

6.8 Contacts with Other RIs

RESILIENCE is strengthening its position in the European landscape of RIs through personal contacts with representatives of other RIs and through participation in SSHOC via its Governing board, Assembly and the Working groups dedicated to data, communication, and impact. In addition to SSHOC, contacts have been established in 2025 with EHRI (especially on possible shared activities on TNA management and Impact

assessment), E-RIHS (on service provisioning) while others are going to be developed with other RIs within the SSH-cluster in 2026, around possible applications to EC open calls.

6.9 Communication and Dissemination Materials

During the reporting period M28-M42 the number of communication and dissemination materials expanded with:

- a video explaining our vision and mission: "RESILIENCE Inside: 5 things to know".
- an InDesign template for a (printed or digital) Training Program.
- Adobe XD generated visuals for the fourth and fifth TNA Call for Applications.
- visualization of the RESILIENCE Impact Pathway Model.
- visualization of the impact stakeholders.

Besides, the general PPT was updated, as well as the A3 (printed) poster and the RESILIENCE Press Release template. Other available materials include: A4 cover folder, Business Cards, Microsoft Office Templates, A3 poster, A5 note block, Online poster for presentations, Roll up banner, A5 service cards (ReIReSearch and TNA), A6 card (general), Fact sheet, Vision/Mission Statement.

6.10 Launch User Services Catalogue

The launch of the User Services Catalogue (D2.2) in M43 provides an excellent opportunity to raise awareness of RESILIENCE among the target groups in the following ways:

- Press release distributed to more than 1.000 addresses in the various target groups and via the consortium partners (delivered).
- Social media campaign in 2026 (in preparation).
- Website presentation, foreseen early 2026, presenting the services on lists in different categories and linking to partner's webpages (in preparation).
- Service-oriented campaign during the annual conference of EuARe 2026 (in preparation).

All these dissemination activities should make clear what it means for the user and how services relate or how a service relates to RESILIENCE vision and mission. In other words, it is not about telling what was done, but what was achieved for the users.

6.11 Publication of the Data Management Plan

The publication of the Data Management Plan (D2.4) in M40 prompted news dissemination: A website article and further dissemination via social media and the newsletter invited people to submit data for the RESILIENCE-community on Zenodo. In addition, the GLAM sector was called upon via mailing to 258 addresses and generally via social media and other channels to make their data discoverable via ReReSearch, but no reactions were received to date [13/01/2026]. It is advised to further investigate the reasons for non-responsiveness. To date, the call for contributions to the Zenodo community yielded 3 records from the wider audience. 31 records were uploaded by RESILIENCE-partners.

7 Best Practices and Challenges

This chapter provides an overview of the main best practices and challenges. The content is a further elaboration of what was described in the previous chapter and in the Appendix, Attachment 1 (Report WP4 Statistics M1-M41).

7.1 Best Practices

7.1.1 Religion and the EU, Roundtable in Brussels

The event "Religion and the EU: a Perfect Match?" held May 7, 2025 in Brussels in which representatives of various institutions and organizations participated, was one of RESILIENCE's highlights as it offered valuable insights into the significance of research on religion for society, culture and for science to the ca. 45 participants, mostly representatives from EU bodies and decision makers. The event was prepared in good collaboration between WP1 and WP4 and the Delegation to the EU of Emilia-Romagna Region. A first roundtable dealt with the question whether academic research on religion can really have an impact on social society and culture. The second roundtable table focused on the impact of research on religion on policy and innovation and on how RESILIENCE can contribute to that impact. These questions and the responses of the participants coming from the fields of politics, academia and religion, demonstrated both the need and the relevance of RESILIENCE. From a communication perspective the event was very successful, because before, during and after the event, representatives from various organizations made use of the opportunity to exchange and connect, in some cases resulting in follow-up meetings.

Figure 6 and Figure 7: Opening of the Roundtable and Roundtable Discussion, Brussels, M34

7.1.2 TNA Calls for Applications

TNA offers good dissemination opportunities for the RI, both in terms of launching via widely distributed press releases, social media/website posts and via feedback from TNA users. This allows scholars to immediately see how they can make use of the RI's services. The high performance of the TNA dissemination is evidenced by the M1-M41 statistics⁴⁵ and driven by five ⁴⁶ Calls for Applications (2022–2025): 312 social posts (KPI 180), 93 fellowship applications (KPI 30), and broad academic dissemination via H-Soz-Kult and IDW. TNA hosts have been and will be asked to bring visiting researchers into contact with journalists. Publication in media may reach civil society, whereas journalists may have an interest in writing about relevant topics, about the relation between issues in society etc. A lot of time and effort has been spent on keeping the webpages for TNA up to date: Each host is presented on a separate page, containing the following sections:

- Benefits for TNA Users.
- About Us.
- Our Collections.
- Research Groups and Expertise.
- Explore National Libraries and Museums.
- Your TNA Contact.
- Website.

allowing interested scholars to get a good impression of the TNA host and its research possibilities. Web pages about the TNA offering were visited as follows during M27-M41 (whereby “/” stands for the homepage) and whereby only the general page for the TNA host was included in the table).

Page path and screen class	Views	Active users
/	28915	3950
/cfa-tna/	3174	1877
/resilience-tna-application-form/	997	431

⁴⁵ See Attachment 1: Report WP4 M1-M41 Statistics (confidential).

⁴⁶ During the period under review, five calls were launched. The sixth call was cancelled, so that the remaining period can only be used for posting on the remaining TNA stays.

Page path and screen class	Views	Active users
/news/fifth-call-for-applications-transnational-access-fellowships-2025-2026/	846	611
/tna-itserr/	764	449
/tna_fellowship_programme/	715	437
/news/call-for-applications-transnational-access-fellowships-2025-2026/	621	460
/tna-host-ku-leuven/	271	154
/tna-saint-epiphanos/	197	69
/tna-host-university-of-munster/	146	104
/tna-archivio-generale-arcivescovile-di-bologna-aab/	140	77
/tna-host-fscire/	140	79
/tna-host-sofia-university-st-kliment-ohridski/	136	83
/tna-host-university-of-sarajevo/	114	74
/tna-bar-ilan-university/	110	77
/tna-host-volos-academy-for-theological-studies/	99	77
/tna-circse/	93	68
/news/call-for-applications-for-itserr-tna-fellowships-2024-2025/	92	69
/news/itserrs-second-call-for-applications-for-tna-fellowships/	89	65

Page path and screen class	Views	Active users
/tna-host-theological-university-of-apeldoorn/	88	69
/tna-new-georgian-university/	88	61
/tna-bektashi-world-center/	83	60
/tna-j-a-comenius-museum/	78	51
/transnational-access-hosts/	77	48
/tna-warsaw/	66	3
/tna-kadoc/	31	17
/tna-mikado/	13	10

Table 9 Statistics TNA webpages M27-41. Source: Google Analytics

7.1.3 Presence at the Annual Conference of the European Academy of Religion

The annual conference of the European Academy of Religion (EuARE), once referred to as the front desk of the research infrastructure for the study of religion, offers an excellent opportunity to showcase the developments and relevance of R. Every year, R is presented with a presentation table and various events that it organizes itself or sponsors. The conference participants are largely part of the target groups that R has defined for its communication, including researchers at various stages of their careers, politicians, and policymakers, which makes participation not only attractive but above all a no-brainer.

7.1.4 Collaboration with ITSERR

The collaboration with ITSERR, the Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE, has proven fruitful. Content originating from ITSERR could be disseminated. In addition, by joining the RESILIENCE TNA Program as a host, ITSERR made an important contribution to the TNA programme, and the dissemination of the RESILIENCE calls for applications, which led to an increase in reach.

7.1.5 Visualization

Now that the project results are becoming clearer, more content is becoming available that lends itself to dissemination. A growing emphasis has been placed on visualizing these results, which benefits communication. That is why the impact model has been visualized, as has the overview of partners as presented in the general PowerPoint presentation and on the website. Furthermore, a campaign is in preparation that presents the various service categories in a visual manner. These infographic-like images are well suited for dissemination on social media and through other means available to the RI. Examples of visualization can be found in chapter 8 (Impact) and below:

Figure 8 Visual Roundtable Brussels, M34

Figure 9 Visualization USC for PPT Presentation (first version)

Figure 10 Interactive Map Partner Overview (first version)

Figure 11 Zoomable Google Map Based Partner Overview (under construction)

Figure 12 Visualization USC for Website (under construction)

7.1.6 Highlights from the Social Media Statistics M1-M4⁴⁷

During the reporting period, the project reached 207.143 people via the social media channels of all partners and RESILIENCE (M1-27: 112.605 people). Several top posts of the RESILIENCE channels are highlighted below:

X

The top post on X promoted the #voices video with (516 media view, 1.1K people reached):

Figure 13 Example of a Top Post on X with Video

Facebook

On Facebook, the post with the reach of 2076 and 81 interactions is about a workshop held by RESILIENCE at EPHE in Paris:

⁴⁷ Go for more details to the Appendix, Attachment 1, Report WP4 Statistics M1-M41.

Figure 14 Example of a Top Post on Facebook

Instagram

The highest score on Instagram, with a reach of 5880, and 11 interactions, was a post on the publication of five core documents in December 2025.

Figure 15 Example of a Top Post on Instagram

LinkedIn

A top LinkedIn post received 946 impressions (May 2025) covering the event "Religion and the EU: a Perfect Match" in Brussels. There were 100 engagements, resulting in an engagement rate of 10,6%.

Figure 16 Example of a Top Post on LinkedIn

7.2 Challenges

7.2.1 Identity versus Image

Although it is constantly emphasized in our communications that RESILIENCE wants to support academics from all disciplines crossing and crossed by religion, regular feedback is informally received indicating that RESILIENCE is only for theologians. To describe it in communication terms: here lies a discrepancy between how RESILIENCE perceives its own identity (serving the study of religion in all academic fields) and the image that others seem to have of the RI (serving theologians). This discrepancy has not been formally investigated yet.

To respond appropriately to this discrepancy, it is recommended to conduct an image study among the target groups to ascertain their perception of RESILIENCE. This study could be extended to members of consortium partners (not belonging to the core team), to determine the extent to which the RESILIENCE identity is known within the organization. Such a survey would be in line with the advice of the ESFRI reviewers.⁴⁸

The Birkigt & Stadler model⁴⁹ can lay the foundations for such a study, because it shows the relationship between the desired identity and the image that others have. It distinguishes between an organization's identity and image. Identity is the "personality" of an organization. Image (also known as reputation) is the way in which that identity is perceived by the environment. Identity in its turn is determined by an organization's behavior, symbols, and communication style, but especially by the behavior of the organization and its collaborators.⁵⁰

⁴⁸ ESFRI monitoring report 02/07/2025, p. 4: "Furthermore, although the vision is strong, more concrete examples of achieved results or early indicators of impact—particularly in relation to joint services and cross-border use—would add weight to the claims."

⁴⁹ Birkigt, K., & Stadler, M. M. (1986), *Corporate identity: Grundlagen, Funktionen, Fallbeispiele*. Landsberg am Lech: Verlag Moderne Industrie.

⁵⁰ See e.g. webpage Boom, retrieved 23.09.2025: <https://boomstrategie.nl/model/identiteit-met-de-corporate-identity-mix-van-birkigt-stadler>.

Figure 17 The Birkigt & Stadler Model

Such a study could answer the question of how target audiences see RESILIENCE and what measures can be taken to solve the discrepancy between perceived image and identity. Below is a schematic overview of the identity and image of the target audience, with the discrepancy and possible approach listed in the last column. The schematics could be completed and the approach implemented in the next phase with the help of the study.

Target Audience	Identity	Image	Discrepancy and approach
Consortium partners (not belonging to the core team)	RESILIENCE is a European cross-disciplinary research infrastructure (RI) serving the study of religion in all academic fields. It connects research centers, data holders and services distributed all over Europe. It creates new instruments and services for its scientific community.	[TBD]	[Description of discrepancy] <i>Approach related to</i> <i>Behaviour</i> [...] <i>Symbols</i> [...] <i>Communication</i> [...]
Target audience [to be specified]	RESILIENCE takes your research wishes seriously. It investigates what you need for your research and	[TBD]	[Description of discrepancy] <i>Approach related to</i>

	offers the appropriate services. It improves access to digital and physical data. Thanks to RESILIENCE, your research will be faster and more effective.		<i>Behaviour</i> [...] <i>Symbols</i> [...] <i>Communication</i> [...]
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Table 10 Schematic Overview of Identity, Image, Discrepancy and Possible Approach

7.2.2 New Time Frames

Over time, it also became apparent that there were delays and postponements announcing services to be included in the USC due to various causes on the part of the developers. WP2 stressed the importance of being careful announcing services as presented in the beta version of the services catalogue, so it was decided to postpone the series “In our services catalogue”. Collecting services for the final version of the services catalogue took considerably more time than expected, partly because the number of community services is greater than anticipated, resulting in postponement of an extensive dissemination of the availability of services. Concerning RelReSearch, the planned “one click away” series appears to be more difficult to implement than expected. At this moment and while writing this deliverable, the idea is to use the publication of the services catalogue at the end of 2025 as an opportunity to launch a (modest) campaign presenting the services offered by RESILIENCE, emphasizing our Unique Selling Points (USP).

7.2.3 Reconsideration of RESILIENCE’s Narrative

RESILIENCE’s communication and dissemination activities and messages profit from a clear vision and mission statement. However, from feedback it becomes clear that audiences do have a wish that we make it more concrete. While preparing the launch of the services catalogue, WP4 therefore proposed to WP3 to connect the services as concrete proof to various elements of our vision/mission, shortly described as follows:

RESILIENCE:

- serves research on religion.
- offers access to digital and physical sources.
- brings innovation.
- strives for open and FAIR access.
- improves knowledge of and understanding of religion.

This reconsideration should be applied in two aspects, namely the question about the further definition of the physical and digital pillar of the RI and the approach in communication. Until now, the physical pillar was mainly communicated through TNA, but meanwhile there is an understanding that physical can also refer to the identification, curation and possibly digitization of relevant collections and to enhancing networking, mobility and TNA.⁵¹

A USP campaign was intended to be prepared, in close collaboration with WP2 (services). While working on it, it appeared that it was difficult to find evidence for the main (draft) messages of a foreseen USP Campaign:

RESILIENCE is a unique research infrastructure for the study on religion, because

- We offer services related to both digital and physical sources.
- We help you profit from innovations in the study of religion.

However, at that point, it was not yet possible to define the USPs based on the services, because the definition of the services was not yet known. It is recommended that the USPs be defined in the next phase of the project and aligned with the various categories of services that are and will be offered. In any case, the USP of providing access to physical and digital resources needs to be included.

7.2.4 Collecting and Presenting Statistics

Various tools are available for collecting and presenting statistics, including: a tracking file in which each partner records their activities and results, Google Looker Studio, which helps create overviews and graphs, social media accounts where statistics for shorter or longer periods can be requested, the KPI overview in which monthly results are reported and Google Analytics for collecting and presenting website statistics. However, data collection can still be problematic because of missing data and time consuming, because not all collection procedures are automatized and presented in an overview (yet). This is an attention point for the future.

⁵¹ D2.1, Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy, version 03.00, p. 32-33.

8 Impact

8.1 Socio-economic Impact Domains

RESILIENCE's impact analysis became available with the publication of the final version of Deliverable D5.1 in November 2025, an extensive document "explaining how RESILIENCE will measure and show its contribution to research, society, economy, and policy once it becomes a fully operational RESILIENCE Research Infrastructure." The core idea of this Impact Analysis is "that the main impact of the RI comes from its services, because services directly reach users. Governance and internal organisation are still important, but their influence is indirect. Therefore, this analysis focuses on measuring how services create change: for example, through better data access, more trained researchers, or stronger international cooperation."⁵²

The analysis is useful for RESILIENCE's future communication and dissemination for several reasons. First and foremost, also for communication and especially for dissemination services are key: if we want to convince target audiences of the necessity of a RI (communication/dissemination goal 2), concrete experiences and examples of how RESILIENCE enhances research through its services are invaluable.

Deliverable D5.1 defines the impact of the future RI across three pathways on four socio-economic impact domains: Society, Policy, Economy & Innovation, and Human Resources, see fig. 18.

⁵² D5.1, Impact Analysis, p. 7.

Figure 18 Impact Pathway Model

Besides, it defines the stakeholders who shape the research infrastructure, who benefit from it, and for whom both counts:

Figure 19 Stakeholders Who Shape and Who Benefit from the RI, Thus Contributing to Its Impact

8.2 Chances for Dissemination

Although all domains in fig. 18 are important, the domain of society and policy are closest to the (current) target audiences defined for RESILIENCE’s communication, namely Academics and Decision makers. Here there are opportunities for future dissemination and for “sharing knowledge, raising awareness and making RESILIENCE’s results visible and meaningful beyond academia”.⁵³ Another possible approach for future communication and dissemination relies on the impact achieved by RESILIENCE RI and as reported in the future RESILIENCE Impact Hub (the RESILIENCE Impact Assessment Digital Platform). The data gathered there can most likely provide content for dissemination, demonstrating the socio-economic impact the RI generates.

A more in-depth reflection leading to a clear strategic approach and an answer to the questions:

- “How to communicate the impact of the RI best?”

⁵³ D5.1, Impact Analysis, p. 27.

- “How to communicate in such a way that the impact of the RI is maximized?”

provided with a methodology on how to evaluate the impact of the C&D activities is needed, to be done in the next phase of the project. For the moment current messages could be (re)formulated from the perspective of impact, telling the world not just what happened, but what was achieved and for whom.

Stakeholder engagement could be a third point of attention. Deliverable D5.1 defines the stakeholders of the RI, how they contribute to the impact of the RI and how they benefit from it. The stakeholder overview as presented in fig. 19 could lead to a further differentiation of the communication and dissemination target audiences and strategies.

8.3 Subsidiarity Principle

Keeping in mind that in the RESILIENCE ERIC countries will be the RIs members, whereas in each country national nodes will be constituted, it is recommended to apply the principle of subsidiarity to the communication and dissemination strategies. In this context subsidiarity means that communication takes place as close as possible to the target audience, which is via the national nodes. Integrating the subsidiarity principle will increase effectiveness and impact of communication, since the communication comes from an institution that will be better known as the RI’s headquarters, whereas the national node will be able to customize the core message to the target audiences in its network. Applying the subsidiarity principle means a decentral approach, enabling adaptation of communication on local/national context and needs, thus increasing the impact of the communication.

9 Exploitation

The previous version of the plan, D4.2 already briefly outlined how RESILIENCE intends to work with the exploitation of the project results. It described the elements of an exploitation strategy, the exploitation objectives, the methods and strategic steps towards the exploitation of results.

Given the status of the USC, being only a list of core services and available services among partners, it is not possible to implement an exploitation strategy based on exploitable results. The development of a strategic exploitation framework is a task that should be executed in the next phase of the project, in accordance with the growth of the USC toward maturity.

10 Conclusions

The agile approach and the choice of the methodology of the Communication Strategy Frame have proven to be fruitful. It gives the space and flexibility to address developments in the project and insights gained from previous periods. In that sense, the approach can also be seen as a learning process, in which what has been learned is repeatedly explained in the strategies and applied in daily work.

Working with previously developed tools such as KPI overviews and regular reporting, the Action Plan, and the tracking file where all partners report their activities has also proven its worth once again. Based on the agile approach, new insights can and where also be incorporated into these tools. Further use by all partners, particularly of the tracking file, could be better monitored during the project and not just at the end of a reporting period.

National and even regional communication needs continuous differentiation, applied by the presenter who is familiar with the context of his audience and tailors his messages accordingly. It could be investigated whether this approach could be further supported by providing training or sharing success stories.

Advice from reviewers and internal recommendations were successfully implemented, adapted towards new insights or moved on to the next phase of the project because they could not yet be implemented.

Feedback collection from target audiences and measuring awareness and engagement rates demonstrate clearly the effectiveness of the strategies when it comes to creating awareness among target audiences (General strategic goal 1) and stimulating that their perception develops into a growing awareness of the need of an RI for the study of religion, as well as knowing how to make use of it (General strategic goal 2). The willingness to play an active role in the construction of the RI (Specific strategic goal 2) is proven by the fact that several observers (8), associated partners (7) and TNA hosts (14) joined the project in the reporting period M1-M4¹.

Regular contact with the target audience via different tools, channels and touchpoints, where personal contacts are a must, result in better achievements when it comes to convincing target audiences of the necessity of a separate RI and for playing an active role. The definition of USPs and further communication, as well as the content of the latest deliverables among which D1.2, D2.2, D3,2 D3,4 and D5.1 will support this.

Deliverable D4.3 is a helpful tool for developing future and updated communication and dissemination strategies as evidenced by the list of recommendations and future actions in par. 11.

11 Recommendations

This chapter contains recommendations following from the previous chapters, whereas it also lists future actions as mentioned in the deliverable. Both recommendations and future actions are based on the status of the project and the insights associated with it and should be checked on effectiveness and appropriateness in the next phase.

11.1 Recommendations from D4.3

1. Develop a Statistics Dashboard

Explore the possibility of creating a dashboard within the RESILIENCE-platform to automate the collection and visualization of communication and dissemination statistics (to reduce manual workload).

2. Differentiate and Update Communication & Dissemination Strategies

- Prepare more detailed and segmented strategies in the next phase, tailored to specific target audiences, archetypes and contexts: academic, civil society, private sector, GLAM sector, decision-makers, professionals in religious communities or churches (Focal Point 7, RESILIENCE Update 39, par. 3.2.1, 3.2.3, par. 4.2).
- Use the refinement of the user needs in the next phase to update the communication matrix when it comes to description of the needs of the target audiences and the subsequent messages from RESILIENCE.
- Consider recommendations and advices from D4.4, the Study on a Subset of Services.
- Take up collecting and evaluating feedback from communication and dissemination activities in the next phase (Advice reviewers 32).
- Reconsider participation in the social media channel X annually.

3. Strengthen KPI Monitoring, Update KPIs

- Monitor KPIs for the three frames at least every two months to ensure progress and adapt actions promptly.
- Update KPIs in accordance with the targets set for the next phase.

4. Integrate Impact Communication

Reflect on how to communicate the socio-economic impact of RESILIENCE effectively, using insights from the Impact Analysis (D5.1). This includes defining messages that show what was achieved and for whom. Moreover, it is recommended to consider early indicators of the impact of communication and dissemination (par. 4.2, chapter 8).

5. Expand Press Contact Lists

Continue expanding the press contact list, especially for the GLAM sector and civil society organizations, to improve outreach.

6. Apply Subsidiarity Principle

In the next phase and with a view to the ERIC status, decentralize communication through national nodes to ensure messages are adapted to local contexts and audiences.

7. Define Unique Selling Points (USPs)

Define USPs. Prepare a USP campaign aligned with the services catalogue, emphasizing RESILIENCE's unique role in providing access to both physical and digital resources.

8. Improve Feedback Loops

- Implement structured feedback collection and analysis for communication and dissemination activities, differentiating responses by career status and familiarity with the RI. Take also into consideration the publication of D3.2 and D3.4 for improving feedback loops (par. 4.2). and the recommendations in 6.5.4 for improving surveys.
- Consider a review stemming from the user-centered approach and the final product offered for this purpose (the USC) in the next phase or as soon as the official version of the USC (the RESILIENCE Service Portal) is ready.

9. Address Identity vs. Image Discrepancy

Conduct a study among target audiences and consortium partners to identify gaps between RESILIENCE's intended identity and perceived image.

10. Enhance Visual and Digital Communication

- Continue developing infographics, videos, and other visual materials to make complex information more accessible and engaging.
- Consider efficiently developing digital tools and online advertising (Advice reviewers 29.)

11.2 Recommendations from Report WP4 Statistics M1-M41

11. Close the 500K unique-reach KPI early

Increase social media and especially Facebook reach by highlighting the User Services Catalogue (see D4.3, par. 6.9). Consider Q/A threads and co-creating with Eastern Europe partners to exploit their active sharing behavior.

12. Grow newsletter subscribers from 550 → 800

Consider attracting subscribers at the EuARE's annual conference June 2026. Event capture: sign-up at future registration and in follow-ups. Consider using Substack.

13. Tighten Analytics and Reporting Hygiene

- Fix webpage title tracking to eliminate "(not set)".
- Keep the overlap model.
- Standardize the partner reporting cadence (bi-monthly).

Appendix

This Appendix contains following attachments, not part of the public deliverable D4.3.

- Attachment 1: Report WP4 Statistics M1-M41.
- Attachment 2: Action Plan.
- Attachment 3: Links to RESILIENCE Living Documents (TNA Programme Communication Workflow 02.00, KPI overview, Guide for Social Media and Online Collaboration).

Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
A1	28/08/2022	Grant Agreement 101079792

Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
R1	18/11/2022	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan D4.1
R2	07/11/2023	European Commission Review Report
R3	12/02/2025	European Commission Review Report
R4	21/11/2024	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan D4.2
R5	02/07/2025	ESFRI monitoring report
R6	14/11/2025	D1.2, Statutes and Technical Description of the research infrastructure
R7	24/07/2025	D2.1, Services and Implementation Strategy

R8	28/11/2025	D2.2, User Services Catalogue
R9	18/09/2025	D2.4, Data Management Plan
R10	27/11/2025	D3.2, Workshop Proceedings 2nd Batch
R11	27/11/2025	D3.4, Documented Use Cases, 2nd Batch
R12	04/12/2024	D4.4, Study on a Subset of Services
R13	26/11/2025	D5.1, Impact Analysis

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